

CALL	<p>Ministry of University and Research (MUR), Directorate-General for Internationalization and Communication, Notice D.D. 3264 dated 28/12/2021.</p> <p>Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2 "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new IRs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking"</p>
PROJECT TITLE	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
PROJECT ACRONYM	H2IOSC
PROJECT ID	IR0000029
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it
CUP	B63C22000730005
WP	03-Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment
OU	10 – CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	3.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Guidelines for data, services, software platform policy implementation
EXPECTED DELIVERY DATE	30/04/2025
ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE	31/10/2025
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<p>This project is funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU. The views and opinions expressed are only those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.</p>	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	<i>Executive Summary</i>	6
2	<i>Introduction</i>	7
	2.1 FAIR Principles	8
	2.2 Open Access and Open Data.....	10
3	<i>Methodological approach</i>	13
4	<i>Data Policy Implementation</i>	14
	4.1 CLARIN: Data Policy	14
	4.1.1 Submission process.....	14
	4.1.2 Data management	15
	4.1.3 Long term preservation	16
	4.1.4 Access and Authentication.....	16
	4.1.5 Practical Case	17
	4.2 DARIAH: Data Policy	17
	4.2.1 Data Ingestion and Management	18
	4.2.2 Data transformation	19
	4.2.3 Data Exposition	19
	4.2.4 Data visualisation.....	20
	4.2.5 Practical Case: The MetaFAIR Ecosystem with RESTORE Data	20
	4.3 E-RIHS: Data Policy	21
	4.3.1 Data production and storage	23
	4.3.2 Semantic framework.....	25
	4.3.3 Processing	26
	4.3.4 Publishing.....	27
	4.3.5 CASE STUDY: Movida	27
	4.4 OPERAS: Data Policy	28
	4.4.1 Practical case.....	30
5	<i>Quality assessment of repositories, data and metadata</i>	32
	5.1 CLARIN: quality assessment	33
	5.1.1 Practical Case	34
	5.2 DARIAH: Quality Assessment	35
	5.2.1 Practical Case: RESTORE - Smart Access to Digital Heritage and Memory	37
	5.3 E-RIHS: Quality Assessment	37

5.4 OPERAS: Quality Assessment.....	39
5.4.1 Practical Cases.....	41
6 Guidelines for common policies implementation.....	42
6.1 CLARIN	42
6.1.1 Practical Case	44
6.2 DARIAH	45
6.3 E-RIHS.....	46
6.3.1 Practical case: the DataSpace-ISPC project.....	46
6.3.2 Practical Case: 3D Roman Theatre in Catania, in SSHOC project.	49
6.4 OPERAS	51
6.4.1 Practical Case	51
7 Conclusions	52
8 References	53

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
ACDM	Ariadne Catalog Data Model
ARIADNE	Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe
CH	Cultural Heritage
CIDOC-CRM	International Committee for Documentation- Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CRM	Conceptual Reference Model
CRMba	Conceptual Reference Model - Archaeological buildings
CRMpe	Conceptual Reference Model - Parthenos Entities
CRMsci	Scientific Observation Model
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
E-RIHS PP	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science- Preparatory Phase
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
HS	Heritage Science
IPERION CH	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure on Cultural Heritage
IPERION HS	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
RI	Research Infrastructure
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
PARTHENOS	Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies
PEM	Parthenos Entities Model

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Submission workflow	17
Figure 2: Data Life Cycle.....	22
Figure 3: Validation process ILC4CLARIN repository.....	35
Figure 4:Musisque Deoque metadata page in ILC4CLARIN repository.....	45
Figure 5: Homepage of DataSpace.....	47
Figure 6 : Knowledge graph	48
Figure 7:Screenshot DataSpace platform	49
Figure 8: Export from C4D to Blender in OBJ format.....	50
Figure 9:Three different extraction steps from an Extended Matrix.....	51

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 3.1 – “Guidelines for Data, Services, Software Platform Policy Implementation” provides a comprehensive framework for the standardization, consolidation, and alignment of digital resources and research infrastructures (RIs) within the H2IOOSC project. The document addresses key challenges in harmonizing data policies, ensuring quality assurance, and implementing common strategies for interoperability and FAIR compliance across participating infrastructures.

The report is structured into the following main sections:

- **Introduction:** Outlines the objectives of Work Package 3 (WP3), which focuses on bridging gaps among RIs, aligning standards, and reducing interoperability issues across technological, ICT, and scientific layers. It emphasizes adherence to FAIR principles, Open Access, and Open Data policies as foundational elements for the development of a shared ecosystem.
- **Methodological Approach:** Describes the policy management cycle adopted, based on the European Data Governance Strategy, including stakeholder engagement, research, design and development, and implementation phases.
- **Data Policy Implementation:** Examines policies and best practices for managing the entire data lifecycle—production, storage, curation, long-term preservation, access, and authentication—across four major infrastructures: CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS. Each subsection includes practical case studies demonstrating real-world application of these policies.
- **Quality Assessment of Repositories, Data, and Metadata:** Defines criteria and methodologies for evaluating data quality and repository trustworthiness, referencing international standards such as CoreTrustSeal and OAIS. It also presents tools and workflows for metadata validation and FAIR compliance.
- **Guidelines for Common Policy Implementation:** Provides actionable recommendations for harmonizing policies across infrastructures, ensuring interoperability, and supporting the integration of national platforms into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem.

The deliverable concludes with an analysis of current achievements and outlines future steps to refine strategies, enhance FAIRification processes, and strengthen alignment with EU and global standards. These guidelines will serve as a foundation for improving data governance, fostering open science practices, and enabling sustainable interoperability among research infrastructures in the humanities and cultural heritage domain.

Due to project-level deliverable submission deadlines, the information in this document is updated as of M36 (October 31, 2025). However, the authors intend also publish an update version that will reporting the latest development about the services and pilots as soon as they are available. This will provide comprehensive information to inform improvement actions, refining strategic action within the cluster.

2 INTRODUCTION

According to the project proposal, Work Package 3 (WP3) is dedicated to the consolidation and overall alignment of Research Infrastructures (RIs) and priority digital resources produced or utilized. The main objectives are:

- Closing existing gaps within each infrastructure to achieve the maturity threshold defined by the project as an entry point.
- Aligning participating infrastructures to reduce interoperability issues across multiple layers, including but not limited to technological, ICT, and scientific aspects.

the core activities of WP3 include:

- Harmonization of community standards for data documentation.
- Alignment of reference resources.
- Definition of standardized protocols and procedures.
- Development of common policies and implementation strategies for the entire data lifecycle (covering data production, storage, management, curation, and long-term preservation).
- Assurance of data and metadata quality.
- Definition of policy requirements related to IPR, Open Data, and Open Access.
- Additional requirements concerning standardization, interoperability, and related services will also be established.

National digital platforms are implemented, updated, or enhanced within this WP, starting from the diverse initial states identified during WP2 activities.

WP3 oversees all data and service management policies provided by each RI, their implementation, and the corresponding operational procedures, protocols, and standards. The goal is to establish a common framework that enables individual infrastructures to interoperate, exchange data, expose services, and make their digital resources accessible through the National Cloud.

Each national digital platform includes facilities for the:

- research data repositories: dealing with all activities of the data lifecycle like creation, ingestion, preservation, access and reuse and considering the heterogeneous nature of born-digital and digitised data, such as texts, numeric results, images, audio, video, 3D and interactive animations and considers internationally recognized standards pertaining to these data
- research services and tools related to tangible or intangible assets such as massive data processing, data analysis and visualisation, data integration
- research portals: including data and services catalogues, training, help desk
- research collaborative workspaces: data and services sharing, scientific orchestrator manager [Mann et al. 2022] able to define and connect services, even provided by different Virtual Research Environments, in a workflow shared between different remote researchers.

2.1 FAIR Principles

The acronym FAIR indicates a list of principles that can help make research data compliant with Open Science. They were defined between 2014 and 2016 by an expert group made up of researchers, publishers and research institutions, funding bodies, to ensure optimal use of research data [Wilkinson et al., 2016].

The principles are not standards or specifications and act as guidelines providing the capability to implement it in the best method according to the data nature and goals.

The FAIR principles define a set of recommendations for data producers and publishers to guarantee that all data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The emphasis of FAIR is on improving the capability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals.

To be compliant with the FAIR guidelines, data should be:

- **Findable** – Easy to find by both humans and computer systems and based on mandatory description of the metadata that allow the discovery of interesting datasets.
- **Accessible** – Stored for long-term such that they can be easily accessed and/or downloaded with well-defined licence and access conditions (*Open Access when possible*), whether at the level of metadata, or at the level of the actual data content.
- **Interoperable** – Ready to be combined with other datasets by humans as well as computer systems.
- **Reusable** – Ready to be used for future research and to be processed further using computational methods.

The FAIR principles are general and do not give any indication of how they are implemented; thus, to make them more concretely applicable, in the original proposal the four principles were further segmented [GoFairInitiative] as follows:

To be Findable:

F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier. This principle is arguably the most significant because assigning a unique identifier to every element of metadata and every concept/measurement in the dataset removes ambiguity in the meaning of published data.

F2. data are described with rich metadata. The metadata can (and should) be generous and extensive, including descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data. Rich metadata allow a computer to automatically accomplish routine and tedious sorting and prioritising tasks that currently demand a lot of attention from researchers.

F3. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource. Identifiers and rich metadata descriptions alone do not ensure ‘findability’ on the internet. There are many ways in which digital resources can be made discoverable, including indexing. The indexing activity must be more precise in the context of FAIR data.

F4. metadata specifies the data identifier. The metadata and the dataset they describe are usually separate files. The association between a metadata file and the dataset should be made explicit by mentioning a dataset's globally unique and persistent identifier in the metadata.

To be Accessible:

A1 (meta) data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol. This principle states that FAIR data retrieval should be mediated without specialised or proprietary tools or communication methods. This principle focuses on how data and metadata can be retrieved from their identifiers.

A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable. To increase data reuse and to facilitate data retrieval, the protocol should be free and open. Anyone with a computer and an internet connection can access at least the metadata. Hence, this criterion impacts your choice of the repository where you share your data.

A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.

The accessible principle does not mean 'open' or 'free'. Rather, it describes the exact conditions under which the data are accessible. Hence, even heavily protected, and private data can be FAIR. Ideally, accessibility is specified in such a way that a machine can automatically understand the requirements, and then either automatically execute the requirements or alert the user to the requirements.

A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available. Datasets tend to degrade or disappear over time. When this happens, links become invalid and users waste time hunting for data that might no longer be there. Storing the metadata generally is much easier and cheaper. Hence, this principle states that metadata should persist even when the data are no longer sustained.

To be Interoperable:

I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. The main goal of this principle is to provide a "common understanding" of digital objects by means of a language for knowledge representation to be used to represent these objects.

The principle defines some properties that these languages should have. The chosen language should have a formal specification, i.e., the language's syntax and grammar are defined in a precise way. Another requirement is that the knowledge representation language specifications should be shared and accessible so others can read the specifications and learn the language. Finally, in order to support interoperability, the language should be designed to be used in more than one scenario.

I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.

The vocabularies used in data or metadata must be FAIR in their own right so that others, humans or machines, can find, access, interoperate and reuse them. The controlled vocabulary used to describe datasets needs to be documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers. This documentation needs to be easily findable and accessible by anyone who uses the dataset.

I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

The goal is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data.

To be Re-usable:

R1. meta(data) have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. The data publisher should provide not just metadata that allows discovery, but also metadata that richly describes the context under which the data was generated. This may include the experimental protocols, the manufacturer and brand of the machine or sensor that created the data, the species used, the drug regime, etc.

R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence. The principle is about legal interoperability. Clarity of licensing status becomes more important with automated searches involving more licensing considerations. The conditions under which the data can be used should be clear to machines and humans.

R1.2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance. For others to reuse your data, they should know where the data came from, who to cite and/or how you wish to be acknowledged.

R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

It is easier to reuse data sets if they are similar: same type of data, data organised in a standardised way, well-established and sustainable file formats, documentation (metadata) following a common template and using common vocabulary. FAIR data should at least meet those standards. Other community standards may be less formal., but nevertheless, publishing (meta)data in a manner that increases its use(ability) for the community is the primary objective of FAIRness.

The FAIR principles now are widely used by many stakeholders in research data management. However, this does not mean that the framework has reached a fully crystallised final state. In fact, the principles are not intended to be static and the rationale behind them is constantly under reconsideration [FAIRport]. The FAIR principles are thus constantly revisited, updated and refined [Mons et.al., 2017].

2.2 Open Access and Open Data

In the Budapest Declaration (2002) [DWH, 2002] and the Berlin Declaration (2003) [Open Access Declaration, 2003] it is possible to find a clear definition of Open Access.

The Declarations broaden the concept of “access” within the framework of Open Access. They include not only fundamental rights such as reading, downloading, and printing, but also extend to the rights to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl, and mine information. Open access (OA) can be briefly defined as the practice of providing online access to scientific information without any cost to the user, and with an emphasis on reusability. Typically, OA is categorised into two primary models: one pertaining to scientific peer-reviewed publications and the other to non-peer-reviewed academic content. This content encompasses various forms, including journal articles, conference papers, theses, book chapters, monographs, and research data.

Two main models are emerging for open access to publications:

- Self-archiving (often referred to as 'green' open access) involves the author depositing the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository. This deposition

can occur before, during, or after the article's official publication. Some online repositories offer the option to delay access to the article during an 'embargo period.' Certain publishers may request embargo periods, arguing that they help protect the value of journal subscriptions they sell.

- Open access publishing (commonly known as 'gold' open access) ensures that an article is instantly available in open access mode upon publication. In this model, the responsibility for covering publication costs shifts from readers (who typically pay through subscriptions) to the author. These costs are referred to as 'Article Processing Charges' (APCs). Usually, the author's university or research institute or the funding agency supporting the research covers these charges. In other cases, subsidies or alternative funding models are used to cover the costs of open access publishing.

The European Commission has developed the implementation of OA policies that are now spreading in Europe. Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data produced by funded projects can be guaranteed through the Horizon 2020 Programme's requirements and guidelines. According to the Commission, there is no need to pay for information funded from public investment when it is accessed or used by researchers, innovative industries and the public, while it is important to preserve this information over the long term. Both European businesses and public knowledge gain more benefits from this policy.

Various open access publishing models exist, and publishers may employ one or more of these models. Different types of open access are frequently categorised using a colour-coding system. The most widely recognized categories are "green," "gold," and "hybrid" open access.

In the Gold OA model, the publisher provides immediate, free access to all articles and related content on the journal's website [Eve, 2020]. Articles in such publications are typically licensed for sharing and reuse under Creative Commons licenses or similar terms.

In Green OA (Open Access), authors are allowed to self-archive their work. This means that authors can independently post their research to a website controlled by the author, the research institution that provided funding or hosted the work, or to an independent central open repository. This allows people to download the work without any cost or payment. [Gadd et al., 2019]

Hybrid OA (Hybrid Open Access) journals contain a mix of open access articles and closed access articles [Laakso, 2016]. Publishers using this model are partly funded by subscriptions and provide open access only for individual articles for which the authors or their research sponsors pay a publication fee. Hybrid OA generally comes at a higher cost than Gold OA and may offer a lower level of service. A particularly controversial practice in hybrid open access journals is "double dipping," where both authors and subscribers are charged. Due to these issues, Hybrid Open Access journals have been criticised and are not considered to fully meet the open access mandate.

Bronze OA (Bronze Open Access) articles are freely accessible for reading on the publisher's page, but they lack a clearly identifiable license. Typically, such articles are not available for reuse [Piwowar et al, 2018].

Diamond/Platinum OA (Diamond/Platinum Open Access) journals are those that publish open access content without charging authors article processing fees. They are sometimes referred to as "diamond" or "platinum" OA. Since these journals do not charge either readers or authors directly, they often require funding from external sources, which can include revenue from advertising, support

from academic institutions, contributions from learned societies, philanthropic donations, or government grants [Rosenblum et al, 2016] [Normand, 2018].

Black OA (Black Open Access) is a term related to the unauthorised digital copying of paywalled literature through large-scale copyright infringement. This practice allows free access to materials that are typically behind paywalls [Bohannon, 2016] [Green, 2017].

About the open data paradigm, the idea of making scientific data openly accessible was first introduced when the World Data Center system was established in anticipation of the International Geophysical Year spanning from 1957 to 1958. Under the current governance of the International Council for Science, this body supervises multiple World Data Centers dedicated to the twin objectives of reducing the likelihood of data loss and enhancing the availability of data resources. [NRC, 2008] [WDS, 2017]

The use of open data in cultural heritage has become increasingly important in recent years, as it has the potential to transform the way we preserve, access, and engage with our cultural and historical treasures. When applied to cultural heritage, open data can bring a host of benefits to various stakeholders, including museums, libraries, researchers, and the general public.

Open scientific data, also known as open research data, represents a subset of open data that centres on the publication of scientific findings and research outcomes, making them accessible for analysis and reuse by anyone interested [Lipton, 2020]. A fundamental objective of promoting open data is to facilitate the validation of scientific assertions, permitting others to examine the reproducibility of results. Furthermore, open data enables the amalgamation of information from diverse sources, contributing to the generation of new knowledge. [Edwards et al, 2011]

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The methodological approach is developed around a policy management cycle reported in European Data Governance Strategy and Plan [Europeana DS Strategy] that identifies four steps:

- **Stakeholder engagement:** “comprises actions that contribute to the process for identifying, engaging and managing engagement with stakeholders in the development and implementation of data governance mechanisms”
- **Research:** “comprises actions that ensure that scenarios and use cases are identified and articulated, with clarity on the problem statement, so that solutions can be designed relying on objective data, evidence and stakeholders’ input. Use cases are identified through general review needs, legal and policy changes or stakeholder needs.”
- **Design and development:** “comprises actions that translate results from previous stakeholder engagement and/or research actions into tangible policy solutions. These solutions can range from narrow, such as policy statements in relation to a specific topic, to broader actions, such as refining frameworks. Their general or specific nature is identified below every action title.”
- **Implementation maintenance e measurement:** “comprises actions that support the practical deployment, implementation and maintenance of the solutions designed. These are also followed by assessing the impact of the solution undertaken, using data gathered during the implementation phases.”

Based on this process, we started the work taking into account the guidelines of the European Data Governance Act [European Data Governance Act].

In detail, during the Stakeholder engagement phase, in order to collect the information about data policy implementation and the strategies adopted to assure the quality assessment of repositories, the project partners were contacted. Each research infrastructures reported their own activities and strategies in the management of digital resources. Furthermore, the recommendations used in their infrastructures for managing open access and open data paradigms were provided.

The analysis of the collected information aims to define a common strategy (following the fair principles and the open access and open data recommendations) in order to align the several research infrastructures.

4 DATA POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

The section describes the policies for data lifecycle, as regard data production, storage, management, curation and long- term preservation, access and authentication adopted by the four RIs involved in the project. It is conceived as a 'guide to good practice'; as such it includes examples and practical cases. The description focuses on different aspects of the data lifecycle considered crucial for infrastructures and for their specific objectives. The choice of the different Infrastructures to place emphasis on some phases over others derives from the use of different methodological approaches as well as from different types and nature of data produced and used.

4.1 CLARIN: Data Policy

The Italian National Research Council (CNR) is the lead institution of the Italian CLARIN research infrastructure, and the Institute for Computational Linguistics “Antonio Zampolli” (CNR-ILC) is the host of its main infrastructural node, the ILC4CLARIN B centre. The ILC4CLARIN centre hosts an institutional and domain digital repository of language resources and offers linguistic tools and (web) services. While data resources may be deposited and thus stored and made persistent in the repository, tools, and services are simply "catalogued" (i.e. described with relevant and common metadata) and linked to make them directly accessible.

The aim of CLARIN repository is to preserve research data, tools and research oriented services in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities. The repository is configured as a DSpace software developed by the Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics, Charles University, in Prague. In the repository, resources may be stored according to four categories: Corpus, Lexical/Conceptual resource, tool, Language description. Users to submit their resource have to follow the DSpace workflow organised into different phases. It is important to highlight that the repository is not outsourced but is managed internally. The Consortium GARR, the “Italian Research & Education Network”, is the main technical partner and the consultant on storage and High-Performance Computing (HPC) topics.

4.1.1 Submission process

First step requires the login action to the platform. The repository uses single sign-on (SSO) to log the users on the system. This implies that the details on the logging users are stored in their identity providers, as described in more detail in the privacy policy [CLARIN-IT. Privacy policy]. The authentication process may be accomplished on double way:

1. via Federated Login: user access through their organisation [CLARIN AP].
2. via Local authentication [CLARIN-IT. Authentication page].

Once users are logged in the repository, they may start the submission process from the “Submission” section in the User Area. From this point user(s) are guided for the whole process. After having selected the type (corpus, lexical/conceptual resource, tool, language description), users have to describe it according to the metadata elements provided (mandatory or optional) according to the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative schema (DCMI). At the initial stage, the information here concerned the authorship (contact information, organisation, publisher, and possible funding). The next step involves the resource descriptive section where a minimum set of metadata are provided to users.

This information is useful to identify the context of resources including language, size, keywords, media type and a free text description field. Once the minimum information is provided, users are able to upload their resources and select the licence(s) they want to provide. This step is particularly important for further accessing processes and to specify the use people can do with the resource and thus owners are required to be careful about this selection.

Before completing the submission, users can leave comments for reviewers and to review the whole process to check the correctness of the provided information.

Once submitted, the resources are reviewed by editors. The latter domain expert checks if every field is correct and the integrity and completeness of metadata as well the bitstream consistency and IPR.

The purpose of the curation workflow is to ensure the overall quality of the resource offering the possibility to return the metadata and/or the data to the submitters for further changes before the item entry into the repository. To provide facilitation in this process, DSpace includes several automatic tools helping editors to verify and validate metadata and the integrity of the submitted data which are performed by every editor during the curation phase. These tools are designed for different tasks [DSpace] as:

- Virus scan for item bitstreams.
- Profile a collection based on format types.
- Ensure that items have quite and correct metadata.
- Ensure the integrity of items bitstream.

The editing process is performed until editors approve and publish the item(s).

During the publication, items are provided with a persistent identifier (PID) that should be used for referencing and citing. From this moment the items are visible on ILC4CLARIN repository, accessible and shareable to the community according to the specific licences. Tools and software are not deposited but only “catalogued” and linked via URIs making easy finding and accessing them. Third parties that retain full ownership of the data they deposit are responsible for its quality and migration to new data formats. Finally, md5 checksums are checked regularly to ensure the consistency of submissions. A report is sent to the editors and administrators who keep track of all used formats. If there is a new emerging and more commonly used format, we can add it to the recommendation

4.1.2 Data management

During the submission process, the submitter agrees to and accepts the policy which leaves him or her the responsibility for the correctness and quality of his/her submission, its legal status and accessibility, and all related ethical issues, if any. CLARIN verifies that a digital object has not been altered or corrupted the repository using MD5 checksums for all objects and checks it periodically. The repository automatically performs regular checks on the integrity and the file formats of data. A list of supported and known formats is provided and regularly checked using existing tools (e.g., integrity testing of bzip format is done using bzip -t). Files are checked three times (not necessarily by editors). The file extension (file format) is checked and marked as supported, known, or unknown. The repository publishes a statement in which it explicitly states:

- what personal information is fetched from the Identity Provider server of the home organisations;

- what log files are created at various levels (i.e. email addresses, name, timestamp, and the performed action; IP address; signed licences if any);
- what purpose personal data are processed for (i.e. user authentication and identification when signing licences; user authorization in special cases; automated sending of email messages necessary for use of the services --password reset, submission information, etc.--; statistics and development of the service; etc.).

Personal data can be deleted upon request of the user, alternatively, it is deleted automatically after 5 years of inactivity of the user.

4.1.3 Long term preservation

The mission of the ILC4CLARIN repository is to ensure the long-term preservation of the deposited data. For this purpose, it adopts the current best practice following the OAIS reference model recommendations [OAIS] keeping data and metadata available and making research results replicable by reusing datasets and tools. The ingestion process is accomplished via the creation of a Submission Information Package (SIP) through a web-based interface which hides the implementation settings. When the curator approves the submission, the Archival Information Package is generated which contains additional information useful to ensure the long-term preservation. Regarding the long-term storage of digital data, the server storage configuration is a Redundant Array of Independent Disks, RAID5, which by itself ensures data redundancy. In addition to that, ILC4CLARIN schedules night-based replicas of the repository, with automatic data consistency check, on a second twin server computer located in a private network environment. In case of failure of the repository, the replica can be on-line in less than 3 hours. This preservation function encompasses: taking delivery of the dataset ingested, storing it, and ensuring it is archived and accessible, and usable to the researcher community as is the mission of a CLARIN Centre [CLARIN Centre mission]. Any other responsibility regarding custody or rights to copy, transform and store are presented to the depositor in the Distribution License Agreement [DSpace Distribution License].

DSpace, and thus the CLARIN-DSpace repository software, provides two levels of digital preservation. The first approach is "bit preservation" which ensures the integrity of both data and metadata over time regardless of possible changes in the physical storage media; the second one is "functional preservation": even if the file may change over time it remains usable in the future by evolving its original digital format and media. Format migration is a straightforward strategy for functional preservation.

4.1.4 Access and Authentication

Researchers and scholars from several institutions have access to the resources in CLARIN according to the specific licences attributed from proper owners. First of all, users are required to log in via the CLARIN Service Provider Federation selecting their home institution or signing on an account. The authentication facilitates the tracking of resources and thus the respect of their restrictions. User's personal data are safeguarded according to the Code of Conduct for Service Providers, a common standard for the research and higher education sector to protect user's privacy. Access to resources into the repository is guaranteed, along their documentation, until 2025. However, since the scope of the CNR-ILC is to provide long term preservation, thereby ensuring continued access to the resources even after this date. In the worst case scenario that ILC4CLARIN was no longer maintained, resources

will be still hosted in another CLARIN data centre. This operation is made easier by the recommendation agreed upon within the Italian CLARIN-IT Consortium to use the same software for each CLARIN-IT repository.

4.1.5 Practical Case

In CLARIN the data implementation process follows the described workflow. CLARIN Short Guide [CLARIN. Short guide] and the Submission lifecycle guides provide the necessary information to make understand the CLARIN Data implementation policy and make users acknowledge about the specific requirements. In particular, the Short Guide offers a synthesis of the infrastructure organisation and mission, meanwhile the submission guides (lifecycle [CLARIN-IT IL] and deposit [CLARIN-IT. Deposit]) provide all the useful information for researchers, submitters, and users in general, who interact with CLARIN and, specifically, intend to submit their data. In this case, it is essential to respect the criteria for metadatation and to select a file format conformant to the suggested list for the standard resources [CLARIN. Standards]. These guides are made for the purpose of helping users to the best use of CLARIN infrastructure, and to submit their data in the most effective manner compliant to the FAIR and Open Science principles. In any case, before the uploading in the repository, data are analysed by infrastructure curators who are responsible for their validation or rejection. If the item does not respect the criteria, submitters are asked to enhance and submit it again. Validators are only responsible for the correctness of the information and format quality, meanwhile submitters are responsible for the quality of their data.

The following figure (Figure 1) shows the described workflow.

Figure 1: Submission workflow

4.2 DARIAH: Data Policy

DARIAH has actively participated in various research projects dedicated to modelling, mapping, and managing cultural heritage assets. These engagements culminated in the development of a comprehensive data management workflow, tailored to efficiently handle a wide range of heterogeneous digital resources. Within the H2IOSC framework, DARIAH-IT plays a key role in promoting semantic interoperability, data harmonization, and FAIR alignment among participating infrastructures. Its approach is grounded in a data-to-service model, in which datasets undergo a structured process of ingestion, management, transformation, and exposition before being made available as interoperable services.

The resulting data lifecycle model encompasses several fundamental phases, starting from data ingestion and progressing through data management, transformation, modelling, mapping, and culminating in data querying and visualisation, all for resources characterised by unique standards and structures. The primary objective of this data lifecycle is the transformation of isolated datasets into an interconnected, semantically enriched database of heterogeneous data.

To achieve this, DARIAH-IT developed an integrated suite of tools and services aligned with the goal of overcoming data fragmentation and domain-specific silos. These tools form the foundation of the MetaFAIR Ecosystem (MFE), a “fairificator” and resource management environment that enables registration, metadata harmonization, semantic validation, and federated access to digital assets within the DARIAH-IT infrastructure. MFE thus operates as a FAIRification and data governance layer, ensuring that all resources can be shared, reused, and discovered in compliance with common standards.

Furthermore, the FAIRified resources and services curated within MFE are made accessible through AEON (dAriah sErvice Oriented iNfrastructure)—the service-oriented platform developed by DARIAH-IT under Activity 6. AEON allows services to be published, orchestrated, and reused within scientific workflows, enabling cross-domain interoperability and execution of complex data-driven processes within the Community Pilots (WP7). Together, MFE and AEON embody the DARIAH-IT strategy for bridging data management and service provisioning, ensuring consistency and reusability across the H2IOSC federated environment.

DARIAH-IT’s policy emphasizes sustainability and modular reuse. The components developed within its ecosystem—such as MFE, the Digital Philology Hub (DPH), and the Digital Heritage and Memory Hub (DHMH)—are implemented as independent, interoperable modules. The renewed DARIAH-IT Marketplace allows users to search and browse resources in the national in-kind catalogue, while selected services and tools are made accessible through the AEON platform. In the following sections, we delve into the various phases of this data lifecycle.

4.2.1 Data Ingestion and Management

To effectively manage the FAIRification process, DARIAH-IT developed an integrated workflow implemented within the MetaFAIR Ecosystem (MFE) — a multilayered environment designed to handle the entire data lifecycle of cultural and research collections. Building on the experience of the RESTORE and RAISE projects, MFE defines comprehensive strategies to support the recovery, understanding, cleaning, and normalization of collected data and digital objects from heterogeneous GLAM sources.

This ingestion phase is based on reference templates and community standards widely used in the cultural heritage domain — such as EAD, EAC, and ICCD schemas — ensuring that each dataset retains both its provenance and descriptive richness.

Before integration, data undergo a validation and normalization process, during which the system checks consistency, completeness, and conformity to FAIR principles. A custom XSD schema, specifically designed for MFE, provides a semantic bridge between heterogeneous input formats and interoperable outputs, enabling flexible transformation across standards.

The ingestion pipeline also ensures that, in addition to item-level metadata, every collection is accompanied by collection-level information (e.g., provenance, curatorial responsibility, reuse

conditions, and versioning), thus guaranteeing transparency and reproducibility throughout the FAIRification workflow.

This modular structure supports the inclusion of diverse institutional datasets, allowing the integration of data originally produced under different descriptive traditions while maintaining semantic alignment.

4.2.2 Data transformation

During the transformation phase, the MFE workflow implements semantic mapping, modelling, and triplification to convert structured or semi-structured data into machine-actionable knowledge graphs.

This process is achieved through mappings between descriptive templates (EAD, EAC, ICCD, etc.) and shared ontologies, primarily CIDOC-CRM, which provides a conceptual framework for representing entities, relationships, and events in the humanities domain.

The transformation follows these key stages:

- **Mapping and modelling:** Domain experts collaborate with data engineers to align heterogeneous metadata fields with reference ontology concepts, ensuring semantic coherence and reducing ambiguity.
- **Triplification:** Once aligned, data are transformed into RDF triples, establishing explicit semantic relations that enable reasoning and interoperability within Linked Open Data environments.
- **Documentation and traceability:** All transformation steps are recorded and documented to ensure full reproducibility of the workflow.

Through this process, the original data are not only standardized but semantically enriched, making implicit meanings explicit and enabling cross-collection reasoning.

The reference ontology (CIDOC-CRM) acts as a formal knowledge model, structuring data into a coherent graph of entities and relationships, which can be queried and extended. This results in machine-readable and logically consistent representations of cultural information that support complex research questions and integration with external datasets.

Ultimately, this phase ensures that heterogeneous data are transformed into a unified, interoperable knowledge base, ready for publication and reuse within federated research environments like H2IOSC, SSHOC, and EOSC.

4.2.3 Data Exposition

Once the semantic transformation is complete, the resulting RDF graphs are ingested into a dedicated triplestore, typically OpenLink Virtuoso, which serves as the core data repository and query server of the MFE platform. This phase exposes data to end users and external services through a set of interoperable APIs and semantic endpoints.

The exposition layer provides multiple modes of interaction:

- SPARQL Query Interface – a web-based interface enabling advanced users to execute semantic queries directly via SPARQL endpoints, retrieving specific entities, relationships, or datasets.
- Faceted Browsing Tools – user-friendly interfaces, such as Virtuoso Faceted Browser, allow users to explore and filter datasets based on metadata facets or controlled vocabularies.
- Visual Resource Browsers – tools like LodLive enable intuitive visual exploration of RDF data as navigable graphs, connecting entities and relationships dynamically.

Depending on licensing and access policies, users can download datasets in multiple formats (e.g., Turtle, RDF/XML, CSV) and generate persistent links or citations for reuse and referencing.

This exposition framework supports both expert and non-expert users, balancing flexibility and accessibility, and facilitating interoperability with external platforms through open protocols and standardized vocabularies.

4.2.4 Data visualisation

Data visualization in the MetaFAIR Ecosystem goes beyond simple display: it provides an interactive, semantically driven environment that enables users to explore relationships among entities, collections, and concepts across the SSH domain. The design principle is to make data understandable and usable by all audiences, regardless of their technical background.

The visualization interfaces are integrated with the MFE triplestore and offer several functionalities:

- Semantic graph navigation, allowing users to follow linked entities and discover contextual information visually.
- Dynamic filtering and search options, suitable for users with varying degrees of digital literacy;
- Integrated visual dashboards, combining metadata browsing and knowledge graph representation to reveal complex interrelations between people, places, objects, and concepts.

Rather than replacing existing partner catalogues or portals, the goal of this layer is to aggregate and reinterpret data semantically within a unified environment, providing new ways to uncover patterns, relationships, and insights.

By doing so, MFE facilitates cross-domain and interdisciplinary analysis, allowing humanities researchers to interact with large-scale digital corpora in a transparent, FAIR, and interconnected ecosystem.

Ultimately, the data visualization component of MFE represents the user-facing dimension of the FAIR workflow — where complex, heterogeneous information is rendered accessible, reusable, and meaningful within an open and interoperable digital research environment.

4.2.5 Practical Case: The MetaFAIR Ecosystem with RESTORE Data

To validate the functionalities and FAIR compliance of the MetaFAIR Ecosystem (MFE) developed by DARIAH-IT within the H2IOSC project, a set of legacy datasets from the RESTORE (smaRt accESs TO digital heRitage and mEmory) project were selected and re-ingested into the new environment. This practical test aimed to assess the system's capacity to manage complex, heterogeneous cultural heritage data and to verify the effectiveness of its FAIRification workflow.

Context and Objectives

The RESTORE project, coordinated by the Istituto Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR), produced a structured corpus of semantically enriched cultural heritage data describing textual, archival, and artistic materials, with a specific focus on the figure of Francesco di Marco Datini. These datasets were already modeled according to established domain standards (TEI, EAD, EAC, ICCD-OA) and aligned with the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM) ontology.

Their import into the MetaFAIR Ecosystem provided an ideal test case to evaluate:

- the interoperability of pre-existing data models with MFE's multilayered architecture;
- the scalability and robustness of the FAIRification pipeline;
- the preservation of semantic consistency and provenance during reprocessing and publication.

Workflow Implementation

Within MFE, the RESTORE datasets were prepared following the platform's packaging and ingestion architecture, which defines the required structure for collections to be processed. Each dataset was accompanied by:

- formalized metadata schemas;
- mapping files linking digital records to media and controlled vocabularies;
- provenance and licensing documentation;
- standardized directory hierarchies to ensure traceable data ingestion.

Results and Validation

The use of RESTORE datasets in MFE successfully demonstrated the platform's ability to manage complex, multi-standard cultural datasets while ensuring full compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

This activity confirmed the operational maturity of the MetaFAIR Ecosystem as a sustainable environment for data FAIRification and semantic management. The re-ingestion of RESTORE data allowed the DARIAH-IT team to test all functional components of the system — from ingestion to visualization — in a realistic research scenario.

The outcome demonstrates that MFE can transform legacy cultural heritage datasets into fully FAIR-compliant collections.

4.3 E-RIHS: Data Policy

To design and develop the DIGILAB platform of E-RIHS, we are gathering information on how data is produced and managed, focusing on identifying shared protocols, canonical workflows and standards for data manipulations, at each of the data-cycle stages: acquisition, processing, post-processing, investigation and publication. The management of information, and more generally of the data life cycle, is of crucial importance in the Cultural Heritage sector. The current volume and complexity of data are enormously increasing, and they will be more in the coming years, tackling the management of the full life cycle of scientific data.

The digital platform of the E-RIHS infrastructure has to be compliant to the Reference Model defined in the European project called ENVRI [Hidalga et al., 2020]. This model describes the life cycle of data produced in scientific research, from design to collection, curation, processing/analysis, publication and reuse. This cycle applies to both the data and the metadata and illustrates how this is managed by the research infrastructures Figure 1.

Figure 2: Data Life Cycle

Regarding data cycle, the digital platform of the E-RIHS platform, currently under construction, is expected to enable all the following phases:

- **Indexing:** Each element of data can be associated with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
- **Data Ingestion:** this operation can be done through:
 1. Harvesting which, with batch imports and web services, acquires data and/or metadata, managing synchronisation of external data sources with the DIGILAB repository;
 2. Data Entry, allowing the input of data and their respective metadata for each relevant individual case through specific forms.
- **Data Curation.** The data curation step must include:
 1. the mapping of the source data model with the internal data model of the DIGILAB Platform (see paragraph 4.3.2). Standard metadata (e.g., unique identifier of the object, source of information, GPS coordinates if available) and specific metadata of the inserted object should be considered in the mapping activities. The inserted object is enriched with a series of metadata.
 2. Syntactic data curation (e.g., correcting any typing errors).

- **Processing:** The data could be transformed, correlated, and analysed. The data should be also transformed into triples, which are data entities composed of subject-predicate-objects, along with the population of the triplestore database to populate a knowledge graph.
- **Publishing:** The acquired information is expected to be published and searchable through the data itself and its related metadata.

4.3.1 Data production and storage

The DIGILAB platform of the E-RIHS research infrastructure has to respond to the specific needs of its scientific community of reference. E-RIHS is based on an integrated research approach between natural sciences and human sciences to combine the methodologies, resources and tools of the different communities involved in a multidisciplinary perspective. Heritage Science is a transdisciplinary scientific field based on synergistic and transversal dialogue between actors of different origins who possess complementary skills and knowledge. It involves various actors who deal with various aspects related to the study, conservation, interpretation and management of cultural heritage: hard science experts (chemists, physicists, biologists, geologists, etc.), restorers, humanists (historians, art historians, archaeologists, archivists, etc.) ICT experts in the heritage sector.

This specific interdisciplinary approach and the different cultural assets investigated involve the production of very heterogeneous digital resources. The enormous amount of data resulting from research, studies, diagnostic analyses conducted over the years is unfortunately characterised by extreme heterogeneity about the following aspects:

- **Data Type:** the data related to cultural heritage are of several types and include a wide range of information useful for the preservation, management, and promotion of cultural heritage. The most relevant types are as follows:
 - Heterogeneous analytical data resulting from non-invasive diagnostic investigations conducted *in situ* with portable equipment or non-destructive analyses carried out in the laboratory for the characterization of used techniques and materials and for the assessment of the conservation status of the investigated asset (chemical maps, spectra, images of thin sections, etc).
 - Conservation and Restoration Data: These data are related to the conservation grade of cultural heritage, the restoration treatments done, and the physical conditions of artworks or historical objects. Data collection campaigns gather information that can be linked to the survey (such as methods, type of equipment used, and their settings), or they can be related to the data collected during the investigation.
 - Descriptive Data: These data include detailed information about the history, origins, dimensions, materials, techniques, and the author of the cultural objects, artworks, historic buildings, and other cultural assets. All this information helps to describe and to document the cultural heritage area.
 - Photographic materials: Photographic images are essential for visually documenting and recording cultural heritage. Photos can be used for research, conservation, restoration, and promotion purposes.

- Location Data: Location data includes geographic coordinates, maps, and geospatial information that allows for pinpointing the exact location of cultural assets. These data are important for mapping and managing cultural heritage.
 - Geographical Data: Geographical data includes geographic coordinates, maps, and geospatial information that locate the exact positioning of cultural assets. These data are essential for mapping and managing cultural heritage.
 - Historical and Archival Data: These data include archives, historical documents, and information that reveal the history, origin, and evolution of cultural assets over time.
 - Environmental Data: these data describe information about weather conditions (for open-air cultural objects), temperatures, humidity, air pollution, and other environmental factors that can affect conservation of cultural assets.
 - Socio-Cultural Data: These data about immaterial cultural objects encompass information about local communities, cultural practices, traditions, and the interaction between culture and the surrounding society.
- **Data Format:** The choice of the correct format depends on the nature of the data, on planned use, and on the compatibility with standards and requirements. The preservation, promotion, and sharing of cultural heritage requires the effective management of data in appropriate formats. Several data formats are adopted in the cultural context, and they are related to the managed different types: Images (JPG, TIFF, PNG, BITMAP, RAW), Video (MP4, MKV), Text (PDF, DOC, TXT), Databases (SQL DB and NOSQL DATA), 3D Models (STL, OBJ), Geospatial (Shapefile, GeoJSON, KML), data interchange formats (JSON - JavaScript Object Notation, XML - eXtensible Markup Language).
 - **Data Structure:** The structure in which information is collected and modelled is often associated with the type of activity that produces the data to be stored. The data structure used is functional to the activity, suitable for the data format and their type but not for data sharing and referencing. The storage structure is, in fact, unique, making the work done less reusable.
 - **Data technology:** The technologies used for data storage are several and are often very specialised for the data format to be stored and the historical period in which the data were modelled. There are data repositories stored in rigid structures of the file system, in sequential files, in relational databases, in geographic databases, and more. In some cases, data has been stored in the proprietary formats of the software that manages them or in the proprietary formats of diagnostic tools. The issue of technology obsolescence is of significant concern. Storage practices are crucial issues related to general questions such as reusing, interoperability and data sharing. Huge amounts of analytical scientific data (spectra, chromatograms, chemical maps images, etc.) are stored in an organised way on personal computers or servers, most often in proprietary formats. This kind of data storing involves elevated medium-term or long-term risks of loss. Proprietary data formats are most often bound to a specific analytical instrument: if analytical equipment and computers are replaced, data and metadata loss is to be expected. In many cases digital data are still considered temporary: they are used as long as the research continues, then disposed of. Within the Cultural Heritage community, there is, therefore, a crucial need for open, preferably human-readable file formats for long-term archival storage, as well as for interoperability and sharing of data between groups of researchers involved [Fremout et al., 2016]. This topic has been

largely discussed in CHARISMA [CHARISMA] and it is a crucial point in the current project IperionCH, which starts from a review of formats for analytical data.

4.3.2 Semantic framework

E-RIHS infrastructure adopts careful policies about the crucial issues regarding data curation in DIGILAB's design and development. This activity involves, among other things, adding metadata to digital resources to comply with the FAIR principles.

Interoperability and Reuse of the data and metadata are themes that cannot be separated from crucial issues regarding metadata schemas and metadata descriptions for scientific data, and most likely, the community debate will be focused on them in the coming years. Metadata defines the context of analytical data. Without metadata, data would be essentially meaningless. They can be very structured and contain information on the nature of the digital object; sample preparation; measurement, instrument used and instrumental parameters; access, and so forth.

The DIGILAB platform involves the implementation of a model useful for mapping the reference concepts of the domain and the level of metadata persistence. To this end, a preliminary investigation is expected to be underway to have a complete picture of the reference domain and to survey the most important initiatives in the field of Heritage Sciences. Among these initiatives are: the ARIADNE project (Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe) which created his own Catalog Data Model (ACDM) [Gavrilis et al., 2015]; the PARTHENOS project (Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies) and its Entities Model (PEM) founded on the CIDOC-CRM too [Bruseker et al., 2017]; the IPERION CH project (Platform for the European Research Infrastructure On Cultural Heritage) and E-RIHS PP project (European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science- Preparatory Phase) [Meghini et al., 2020]; the IPERION HS project (The Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure On Heritage Science).

Within the E-RIHS.it digital infrastructure, a set of modular ontologies has been developed to represent, in an interoperable manner, the various domains of Heritage Science and to facilitate the semantic integration of data generated by research activities aimed at the knowledge, conservation, and enhancement of cultural heritage.

The ontological system is organized into several components, including:

- **Core Ontology (namespace core:)**, which defines the main entities and fundamental relationships within the ontology network for cultural heritage research data.
- **Digital Resource Ontology (namespace digital-resource:)**, focusing on the representation of digital resources, their distributions, and associated metadata.
- **Cultural Heritage Ontology (namespace cultural-heritage:)**, addressing the cultural heritage research domain, centered on the concept of cultural entities and processes of conservation and analysis. This component models common informational elements of cultural artifacts and integrates with the ARCO Ontology Network developed by ICCD.
- **Manuscript Ontology (namespace manuscript:)**, designed for the specific domain of illuminated manuscripts.
- **Diagnostic Investigation Ontology (namespace diagnostic-investigation:)**, representing techniques, methodologies, and results of scientific investigations conducted on cultural

heritage, including observations, experiments, instruments, acquired data, and corresponding interpretations.

All E-RIHS.it ontologies are developed according to the principles of modularity, reuse, and semantic alignment. They establish explicit mappings and conceptual correspondences with major international standards and reference models, including CIDOC CRM, CRMdig, CRMsci, LRMoo, PROV-O, DCAT, Dublin Core, IoT Ontology, and SKOS.

Overall, the E-RIHS.it ontology network constitutes an open, interoperable semantic infrastructure oriented toward Linked Open Data, capable of supporting the publication of data in RDF/Turtle format and their integration into national and international information systems dedicated to Heritage Science.

4.3.3 Processing

The processing phases is related to all the task:

- To transform the data. Considering that the enormous amount of data resulting from research, studies, and diagnostic analyses conducted over the years is unfortunately characterised by extreme heterogeneity (of data type, of data format, of technology), the data transformation plays a crucial role. It's necessary to have a flexible tool (such as a workflow engine) able to define several steps of transformation configurable by the researchers. The purpose of transformation is to adjust the different data differences to make them suitable for the analysis phase.
- To correlate the data: As previously mentioned, different repositories often do not share the same structure and semantics, making them isolated entities. During the data curation phase, all sources were aligned with the reference ontology. Using common semantics, specific tools can link the different sources to discover new knowledge.
- To analyse the data: The transformed and correlated data must be analysed for example using:
 - Time Series Analysis: Time series analysis focuses on data collected at regular time intervals. It is used to identify patterns, trends, and seasonality in time-dependent data.
 - Cluster Analysis: Cluster analysis groups data points with similar characteristics together. It is often used for customer segmentation, image processing, and pattern recognition.
 - Spatial Analysis: Spatial analysis is used to analyse data with a geographic component. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are commonly used for mapping, geospatial analysis, and location-based insights.
 - Inferential Analysis: Inferential analysis is used to make predictions or draw conclusions based on a sample of data. Statistical methods like hypothesis testing and regression analysis are used for this purpose.

In detail E-RIHS DIGILAB platform offers researchers advanced tools for data processing and analysis, enabling transformation, correlation, and interpretation of both proprietary and shared datasets. The platform integrates a robust computational environment with services for enrichment, visualization, and statistical evaluation. A key feature is its extensive use of an ontological layer, ensuring semantic interoperability and enabling complex correlations across heterogeneous data sources.

4.3.4 Publishing

Publishing scientific data is a fundamental aspect of the research process that involves making research findings and data publicly available. Information publishing serves as a vital conduit for sharing knowledge, research, news, and insights.

It promotes transparency, collaboration, and the open exchange of knowledge. Open access to data empowers researchers to build on each other's work and contributes to the cumulative nature of scientific discovery.

Providing an access point for different stakeholders to access the collected and processed data is crucial. In particular, researchers must be able to search for information based on keywords and leverage metadata using the concepts and thesauri present in the reference ontology.

The result of the data must be presented in the most suitable format for the data itself: graphical or tabular. Exploring information through a knowledge graph should be possible using semantics, which allows the researcher to navigate through semantically linked data.

In E-RIHS DIGILAB platform, the publication process ensures validated data and metadata are published in a structured way, making them accessible and searchable through the Data Portal and Data Catalog. The Data Portal provides the main user interface with visualization tools, faceted browsing, and semantic navigation, while the Data Catalog offers a standards-compliant metadata repository to support data and metadata lifecycle management, interoperability, and integration with external systems. This dual approach guarantees discoverability through both data and rich metadata, ensuring FAIR compliance, long-term accessibility, and reuse.

4.3.5 CASE STUDY: Movida

Heritage Science is a multidisciplinary domain distinguished by the convergence of heterogeneous data, methodologies, and techniques. Within this context, research data are often stored in isolated repositories, which are frequently inaccessible to other scholars in the field. Moreover, diagnostic investigations applied to Cultural Heritage typically involve a wide variety of tools, protocols, configurations, and data formats. At the same time, the scientific investigation process itself is not always adequately documented, making replication difficult or even impossible.

This fragmentation poses a significant challenge and underscores the urgent need within the scientific community for effective tools capable of analyzing, transforming, and correlating information originating from these disparate sources. To address these needs, we are developing a new digital application designed for the collaborative management of data derived from multi-technique, non-invasive investigations of artworks. The application is expected to enable the storage, analysis, and advanced visualization of diagnostic data related to Cultural Heritage.

The application, named DIGILAB Mobile Diagnostic Data Manager, is part of the DIGILAB platform, which constitutes the Italian node of the E-RIHS research infrastructure and is currently under development within the H2IOSC project. DIGILAB aims to provide an interoperable ecosystem of data, tools, and services to support research, publication, conservation, enhancement, and interpretation of Cultural Heritage.

The DIGILAB Mobile Diagnostic Data Manager (denominated MDDM – Movida 2.0) builds upon the MOVIDA (MOBILE laboratory VISualization DATA) tool, extending its capabilities beyond point analyses to fully support imaging, mapping, and geophysical scientific). It is designed as a comprehensive and innovative platform for managing and supporting research workflows. MDDM – Movida 2.0 has been designed in close collaboration with the E-RIHS research community and adheres to the SaaS (Software as a Service) paradigm, offering secure cloud-based data storage. It is extensible, allowing the integration of new investigation techniques and custom metadata schemas, while ensuring long-term preservation, FAIR principles compliance, and collaborative workflows.

Through its integration within the DIGILAB ecosystem, the system maps its resources onto the ontological data model developed for scientific investigation information. This approach contributes to the construction of a multidomain knowledge graph for the Heritage Digital Twin, thereby enabling advanced knowledge discovery and supporting innovative research scenarios.

For more detail about Movida 2.0, refer to Deliverable 3.2 paragraph “3.5.8.3 Mobile Diagnostic Data Manager (MDDM – Movida 2.0).

4.4 OPERAS: Data Policy

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. It is not specifically dedicated to the management of research data but rather to the scholarly communication and publication needs of European researchers, primarily in the field of SSH.

Its aim is to make Open Science a reality for research, providing support and services to the scholarly communication system with a strong accent on cooperation, federation of existing resources and practices, and supporting open documentation and publication through tools for evaluation, discovery, and fruition.

In order to meet the scholarly communication needs of researchers, OPERAS is specifically committed to: a) fostering and expanding two-way access to research outputs and resources; b) consolidating the Open Science and Open Publishing Resources through a data lifecycle approach that encourages research community awareness and collaboration.

The Italian node is oriented towards the efficient and effective support of the management, provision and publication of research results (<https://monitor.openaire.eu/support/terminology-and-construction.html#entities>) and research data in a broad sense (including datasets, collections of digital resources, documentation of research activities, digital scholarly editions, open handbooks, and open publications in general). On the other hand, it seeks to devote special attention to, as well as generate and collect original data about the status and development of open science practices in the national context.

For the purpose of achieving these objectives, and, in particular, within the scope of the H2IOSC project, the initiative has been taken to produce tools, platforms, services, training materials, workflows for creating, managing, perusing and visualising, as well as finding, accessing and reusing such data. On the background of OPERAS’ fundamental policy orientations, the acquisition, production, and management of digital resources and data assets that derive from the activities of the Italian node privilege, in the sense described in “Data governance and data policies at the

European Commission”, EC 2020¹ the “need to share”, or “share by default” principle: free, full, open and timely access. Clearly, of the four SSHOC criteria for inclusion,² the “degree of compliance with Open Science” is privileged. Conformity to FAIR principles is warranted and, whenever it is the case, the appropriate application of the CARE principles is corroborated.

In this context, the technologists, researchers, research groups, and institutions of the Italian node can operate on occasion in a number of capacities: on the one hand, as data producers, data owners, and also data users; on the other hand, as data steward, data custodian, and data provider. In the latter roles, they are expected to

- implement appropriate controls;
- set protection and delivery standards;
- manage various levels of open access rights and, possibly, layered business models.

Furthermore, they are expected to involve the researcher of the research community, in turn, as data producers, data owners, and data curators, thereby ensuring that the quality of digital resources is a communal undertaking. Befitting instruments are made available, and in the Italian node’s platforms and tools an appropriate shared governance of the resources is expected to be put in place, adequately involving the various stakeholders. The same principles must inform the design of tools and platforms that catalogue, aggregate, and expose resources to the users, or allow the users to interact with them: this is particularly valid for the design and development of the H2IOSC MarketPlace (see below).

Consequently, in the production, management, and delivery of digital data and resources, open methodologies and standards are systematically favoured and, when appropriate, required. The resulting open digital resources are collected, managed and published in various forms corresponding to the customs, needs and innovation paths of the scientific community. Such open standards are to be used, moreover, that are developed and fostered by the scientific community and the communities of users of scientific resources and results (standards or commonly agreed specifications for representing digital resources may be specific to a research domain).

The handling and processing of data shall be publicly documented, and data are to be shared with open licences: always as open as possible, while closed only as strictly necessary. Digital objects must be provided with standardised, as rich as possible, metadata, identifying the resources, the owners and curators, the forms of delivery and ways to access, as well as the reuse conditions, exposed directly and/or through shared platforms and the H2IOSC MarketPlace. Specifically, standardised persistent identifiers are used to identify digital objects and data assets.

This overall approach is also reflected in the pilot services/platform that have been and will be produced by the OPERAS OUs in H2IOSC, aimed at facilitating Diamond Open Access publishing of different kinds of scientific outputs and resources. Specifically, the aim of OPERAS activities in this WP can be succinctly described as:

- a) to promote two-way access and actively contribute to the main innovative OPERAS services;

¹ See https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-07/summary-data-governance-data-policies_en.pdf.

² See <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/about/data-population#inclusion-criteria-for-adding-resources-4-questions-to-ask>.

- b) to develop OPERAS Diamond capacity building for Diamond OA publication of journals and monographs;
- c) to provide access to OPERAS Certification tools and services for the national scientific landscape.

The OPERAS OUs, in collaboration with the Italian national node and the central legal entity OPERAS aisbl, are requested to achieve these goals in the H2IOSC project by:

- developing actions and facilities, both at the general level of the cloud platform marketplace, and
- providing pilot services/platform specifically intended to manage and use research data, resources, and further services, according to European standards and requirements for open science and open data (FAIR).

These activities directly and effectively contribute to the implementation of a collaborative workspace for H&CH research that will foster open data sharing and reuse.

4.4.1 Practical case

The development of the H2IOSC MarketPlace in WP5 has been the main focus point in the first project phase for the OPERAS OUs. Its main objective is to create a unique access point to datasets, tools and services as developed in other WPs, in particular WP6 and WP7. It enables research data to be found, processed, enriched, analysed, used, managed and effectively re-used beyond the borders of hosting repositories and single institutions.

The Marketplace has to be aligned with the national and European catalogues of the participating RIs and with the portals and catalogues of other European and national research infrastructures, in particular with EOSC and SSHOC. Data and metadata are formalised according to the common semantic knowledge framework, developed in WP4; full compliance with the FAIR principles is also guaranteed.

A specific data model has been developed for the main functionality of the Marketplace, that is, the catalogue. Its entries consist, in this model, of descriptions of *Tools* and *Aggregations*.

Tools are descriptions of physical or digital services, while *Aggregations* – as the name implies – are more complex services, composed of multiple tools, used together to fulfil a specific research need. The detailed description of a Marketplace entry therefore presents either the tool or the aggregation: in the latter case the tools in the aggregation must be mentioned and a link to their descriptions provided. Different aggregations can share the same tools. It is also possible to compare each tool or aggregation with other relevant entries in the catalogue, based on various criteria that have to be identified during the requirement analysis phase (e.g., similar tools/aggregations, alternative options for carrying out the same research activity, additional offerings from the same service provider, etc.). The users, reading the descriptions, can choose the items (tools or aggregations) that satisfy their present research needs, as well as other functionalities. The Marketplace is to be intended in fact an articulate platform and the users should be guided to easily navigate through its various sections and services.

To this purpose, in the model, the services associated with the Marketplace are grouped in Levels.

Level 0 services are those that the Marketplace offers but are not listed in the catalogue. They are specific to the Marketplace and their aim is to enrich the user experience. Examples of *Level 0* services include:

- User-oriented functionalities (navigation, personal and shareable lists of “favourites”, personal workflows...)
- Governance-oriented functionalities (administration, decision support services, measurement, evaluation, statistics...)

At **Level 1** we have the tools, as defined before, while at *Level 2* we find the aggregations. Their detailed description is different. Tools descriptions include the instructions (and the link, in case of a digital service) to access and use them. Tools include digital services, e.g. software packages, datasets, web platforms and the like, together with physical instruments offered by the laboratories of the participant RIs. External services acquired from third parties (e.g. by automatically harvesting external catalogues, like those of EOSC or SSHOC) are listed as Level 1 tools.

Level 2 aggregations are typically composed of pilot services and platforms, in particular those implemented in WP7, which mainly develops *Level 1* tools. As functionalities available through the Marketplace, they shall be generalised and made pluggable/interoperable, in order to be exploited by other H2IOSC implementations, in particular by the other pilots developed in WP7.

5 QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF REPOSITORIES, DATA AND METADATA

The concept of quality of an archive varies in relation to the scientific community of reference and can take on very different meanings even within the same community depending on the project or research initiative. There are different perspectives between disciplines and even within the same disciplinary areas. This derives from the use of different methodological approaches, different levels of digital literacy, as well as the different types of data produced and used.

For the assessment of research data, H2IOSC uses the FAIR principles as a general framework for verifying the quality and the correctness of data.

Data and metadata are ideally stored in a digital archive that complies with established quality requirements, to ensure the adequate preservation, dissemination and accessibility of research data. About the quality assessment of repositories, in recent decades, tools have been developed and methods defined to evaluate their quality and help organisations evaluate the current state of development, indicating the critical issues to be addressed and resolved to meet certification requirements.

Like the FAIR principles define the properties of data, the document "Trusted Repositories Audit & Certification" [Giaretta, 2011] establishes the properties of repositories to grant certificates. Trustworthy Repositories Audit & Certification (TRAC) describes the metrics of an OAIS-compliant digital repository [ISO14721] that is developed from work done by the OCLC/RLG Programs and National Archives and Records Administration (NARA) task force initiative. According to TRAC, the mission of a trustworthy data repository is to "provide reliable, long-term-access to digital resources, now and in the future." The process of certification requires a complete understanding of the threats and risks to the data within its systems and a regular cycle of audit and/or certification.

Three increasing levels of trustworthiness are defined:

- 1) The repositories certified with the DSA certification (Data Seal of Approval) obtain the Basic Certification.
- 2) Extended Certification is granted to Basic Certification repositories which in addition perform a structured, externally reviewed and publicly available self-audit based on DIN 31644: nestorSeal.
- 3) The Basic Certification repositories certified with full external audit and certification based on ISO 16363 obtains the Formal Certification.

The first two levels are based on self-assessment, combined with external review. The third and highest level, the formal certification, however, is based on a full external audit. To support the organisation in the repository certification process, there are several tools and models. The Community Owned Digital Preservation Tool Registry (<http://coptr.digipres.org/>) provides an up-to-date list of digital preservation tools (including tools for ingest).

In line with the planned activities, we have introduced a census (described in this chapter) on "policies related to the quality of data, metadata, and repositories" with the goal of modelling a set of common policy implementations.

5.1 CLARIN: quality assessment

CNR-ILC is active in the standardisation of linguistic data formats: it hosts the chairperson of the ISO TC37 SC4 – Language resource management [ISO/TC 37/SC], and expert members of some of its committees, nominated by the Italian standardisation body (UNI) [UNI]. By being part of the CLARIN federation of technical centres, ILC4CLARIN is in constant contact with experts in all the CLARIN ERIC member countries, in particular with those working at B and K centres [CLARIN B and K centres]. ILC4CLARIN is also the national data centre of the Italian CLARIN Consortium (CLARIN-IT) [CLARIN-IT Consortium], whose coordinator regularly participates in the CLARIN ERIC coordination activities and major events. Furthermore, the ILC4CLARIN repository Technical manager is the Italian representative to the Standing Committee for CLARIN Technical Centres [CLARIN SC] which coordinates the activities of all CLARIN technical centres Europe-wide and takes decisions on implementation.

As required by CLARIN ERIC, ILC-CNR for CLARIN-IT goes by periodic assessments (every 3 years). The assessment is performed through the CTS, formerly (DSA). The actual certification is valid for the period august 2023-august 2026 in respect of CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2020-2022 [Core Trust Seal].

Concerning the quality assessment of data, the repository adopts various standards:

- The repository relies on the group of emerging metadata standards around CMDI (ISO-CD 24622-1 Language resource management) [ISO 24622-1:2015]. This ensures that the metadata required to interpret and use the data are provided and are sufficient for long-term preservation.
- CMDI Profile schemas are based on the W3C XML Schema standard and refer to the CLARIN Concept Registry [CLARIN CR] (previously ISOcat), a concept scheme model based on SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) [CLARIN Concept Registry]. CMDI profiles used are published here: <http://catalog.clarin.eu/ds/ComponentRegistry/#>
- OAI-PMH (v2) protocol standard for metadata harvesting; the repository makes metadata formats available via the repository's OAI-PMH endpoint. Metadata are made available according to the CMDI 1.2 metadata specification and are harvested via the repository's OAI-PMH endpoint. CLARIN ERIC harvests our CMDI metadata to a central registry, which can be seen at CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory[CLARIN VLO].
- The repository database and HTML web pages use the UTF-8 encoding standard, for correct character encoding.
- ISO language codes in metadata during the submission process.
- Variety of data formats for the submitted digital objects. Successively to the submission, data cannot be changed. This ensures that data is authentic and it is also important for the assigned persistent identifiers, which must always refer to the same content. For changes, submitters should contact the help-desk for requesting it.
- Language resources recommended formats, referred by CLARIN at: <https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/Standards%20for%20LRT-v6.pdf>.

The repository is developed to allow users a full implementation guide to the submission of their data. According to that, the submission interface and workflow guide the user in providing relevant and complete (meta)data. If the minimum information required is not provided, the interface does not allow the user to complete the submission. After submission, the item is then reviewed by the metadata curators that check for the quality of the metadata. Editors are also responsible for verifying that the data submitted corresponds to what it describes, meanwhile a thorough check of the quality of the data however is not performed since it is beyond our mission and scope. As declared previously, in the Distribution Licence Agreement it is stated that depositors are responsible for the quality of their data and are expected to deliver data living up to academic standards. In case a submission does not comply with the expectations of the repository, it is returned to the data provider for rectification, via the interface.

The same quality checks (i.e. evaluation of the relevance of the data for the repository, metadata completeness and correctness, verification that the data described corresponds to the actual accessible/downloadable data), apply also to data that is not physically held by ILC4CLARIN but only catalogued. The validity of the submitted data sets is checked manually by an expert editor.

About the risk assessment approach to the recommended formats of submitted items, metadata curators manually verify eventual attached bitstreams. Metadata curators are, obviously, in contact with the depositor(s) to obtain missing information if there is any. If the format is unknown or not in the list of the recommended standard formats, it must be well documented and the documentation must be either part of the submission or the metadata must contain a link to it. However, the final decision on the acceptance/rejection of such submissions is taken by the ILC4CLARIN metadata committee in collaboration with our repository administrator.

All datasets/resources added to any collection are assessed for quality in the same way. Collections are simply virtual containers for resources belonging to a conceptually homogeneous pool (e.g. an institution, an archive, etc.). All resources within a collection are individually described with the full stack of metadata [DSpace MD].

In addition, the technological upgrade of the ILC4CLARIN repository from DSpace 5 to DSpace 7, described in detail in Deliverable 3.2, further strengthens the quality assurance framework by providing a modern architecture with enhanced metadata management, improved accessibility, and extended interoperability features.

5.1.1 Practical Case

The data assessment is the key moment for the final validation and submission into the repository. To support authors and curators to improve the quality of their metadata, CLARIN-ERIC hosts and maintains the Curation Dashboard [CLARIN. CD] originally developed by the technical team of the ACDH-CH [AAS].

Curation Dashboard is a software bundle, which determines and grades the quality of metadata harvested by CLARIN for language resources and consists of three parts:

- 1) stand-alone application for reports generation (curation-core). This module does the actual analysis of individual CMD profiles, records and whole collections according to a number of quality criteria and generates reports and statistics which help discover potential problems that cause a lower metadata quality;

- 2) web application (curation-web). The user facing web application that offers four main functions:
 - on the fly validation of individual profiles and metadata records (either by their URLs or uploading them as files);
 - presenting pre-computed statistics for CMD profiles;
 - presenting pre-computed statistics for collections;
 - presenting pre-computed statistics for link checking and a continuously generated statistics in detail view (hence values might differ if links of the provider have been checked in the meantime);
- 3) stand-alone application for link checking (linkchecker). It checks constantly and repeatedly all the URLs contained in metadata records of the collections. The Core module later uses these results to generate statistics and takes them into consideration when assessing the quality of the metadata. Additionally, the results are also used by the CLARIN metadata catalogue, the VLO, to indicate the availability of a resource. This module is maintained in a separate code-base.

The Curation Dashboard processes publicly available CMDI records, collections and profiles. It grades them and gives them scores based on different quality aspects. It also provides information on them and on what properties were graded.

Figure 6 shows the activities during the validation process on the repository curators.

Figure 3: Validation process ILC4CLARIN repository

5.2 DARIAH: Quality Assessment

DARIAH developed strategies to ensure the integration and interoperability of data provided by different institutions (archives, museums, libraries, research centres, etc.), including national cultural and research entities. The primary objective of the work done for the Arts and Humanities Data communities was that of publishing a workflow allowing for the semantization of datasets, accomplished by the use of free and open access tools. DARIAH's quality assessment policy aims to

extend this approach, offering technological and infrastructure support to other entities with similar needs, as well as to operators in the cultural and creative industries. This approach is implemented through the MetaFAIR Ecosystem (MFE), a modular and scalable environment that manages the entire FAIRification process—from data ingestion and semantic enrichment to publication and reuse.

DARIAH developed solutions aligned with the FAIR principles to address several key challenges in managing digital assets and ensuring conformity to FAIR principles and criteria. These key points include:

Ensuring Data Quality

Solution: Validation, Cleaning, and Provenance Control

Data quality assurance in DARIAH-IT is performed through MFE’s ingestion and validation layer, which automatically checks metadata completeness, structural coherence, and compliance with reference templates (e.g., EAD, EAC, ICCD).

The process involves collaborative cleaning and normalization performed side by side with data providers, supported by domain experts to ensure conceptual accuracy and contextual integrity. The inclusion of collection-level provenance metadata—covering origin, responsibility, and reuse conditions—guarantees the traceability of each dataset.

All ingestion and transformation steps are documented and versioned, ensuring transparency and reproducibility in line with FAIR principles. By integrating data verification, semantic modeling, and automated quality reporting, DARIAH ensures that research data remain reliable and sustainable throughout their lifecycle.

Ensuring Interoperability

Solution: Common Ontologies and Semantic Alignment

Interoperability is achieved through the use of shared conceptual models, most notably the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM), which provides a standard ontology for representing cultural heritage artefacts and their relationships.

Within MFE, this ontology serves as the semantic backbone for mapping heterogeneous datasets into coherent knowledge graphs. Mappings between domain-specific templates and ontological classes are defined within MFE’s configurable pipeline, allowing the automatic transformation of normalized data into RDF triples. This architecture guarantees semantic alignment and supports integration into federated environments such as SSHOC, EOSC, and H2IOSC

Guarantee Legal Compliance

Solution: Harvesting, Management, and Training

DARIAH-IT promotes compliance with European and national regulations by implementing a comprehensive data governance framework that encompasses legal, ethical, and technical dimensions.

This includes:

- Adoption of standard licensing and provenance documentation to ensure proper attribution and reuse conditions;
- Implementation of security protocols, including controlled access, backup systems, and disaster recovery measures;

Through these measures, DARIAH-IT ensures that its infrastructure operates in full compliance with the FAIR and Open Science principles, while safeguarding the legal integrity of all digital assets

5.2.1 Practical Case: RESTORE - Smart Access to Digital Heritage and Memory

The MetaFAIR Ecosystem has been tested using datasets from the RESTORE project, allowing DARIAH-IT to validate its FAIRification workflow through real-world, semantically rich collections. The imported datasets underwent all stages of the MFE process—ingestion, validation, semantization, and publication—demonstrating the system’s ability to manage heterogeneous cultural heritage data while maintaining semantic precision and legal compliance. This practical application confirmed the robustness and reusability of MFE as a quality assessment and FAIRification tool, capable of transforming legacy resources into machine-actionable, interoperable, and ethically managed datasets for the broader research community.

5.3 E-RIHS: Quality Assessment

As written previously, the concept of quality is quite different in the different research sectors.

In the domain of Cultural Heritage, the quality is strictly connected with the quality of managed information. In many cases, the value of information depends not only on its characteristics such as the structure and the accuracy but also on the entire life cycle of data that generates the information itself.

The quality assessment of the HS domain must be based on information aspects and, in detail, on information characteristics and its processing.

Focusing on the characteristics of the information, the compliance with the FAIR principles, and the resulting use of a common ontological layer to metamodel data are the main elements of quality assessment. The information processing addresses issues concerning data curation, data life-cycle.

In the following, we describe the requirements that E-RIHS [E-RIHS PP - D5.3] implements to ensure the respect of FAIR principles and, thus, the desired quality level; while in the next few months, we will investigate the characteristics of the information processing.

The Findability principle

1. Every data repository and, in general, every resource of E-RIHS must be referred through persistent identifiers that must be output in every research.
2. Every resource in the digital platform of E-RIHS must be easily cited by users, using persistent identifiers. This requirement is derived from best practices in data citation in the heritage science research community.

3. Intensive use of the ORCID identifier for the E-RIHS user. The ORCID identifier is unique, and it could be used as a user identifier in the research community.
4. Metadata is crucial in the findable principle; thus, E-RIHS must promote the metadata use and the continuous development of relevant metadata schemas to include more information in its domain.

The Accessibility principle

- All digital resources and services must be accessible and can be retrieved in the easiest possible way. A large use of standard communication protocols must be done.
- E-RIHS should guarantee that all the repositories could be suitable in time and not be affected by technology obsolescence.
- The quality of E-RIHS repositories should be guaranteed by necessary certification
- E-RIHS researchers should take into account legal obligations, policies specific to their disciplines, and ethical protocols where applicable.
- E-RIHS repositories should ensure that (meta)data is widely accessible and can be harvested by search engines, significantly enhancing accessibility
- DIGILAB, as part of E-RIHS framework, could be provide a registry of protocol endpoint to allow the exploration of its catalogue
- E-RIHS should offer best practice guidance to ensure that new and emerging repositories are structured optimally for reuse within the E-RIHS data ecosystem.
- E-RIHS should assist repositories in enhancing the accessibility of data linked to publications.

The Interoperability principle

- E-RIHS should endorse interoperability standards that are both usable by humans and machine-readable.
- E-RIHS should encourage the development of active user communities based on standards for heritage science.
- The resources model of DIGILAB E-RIHS must be based on the metadata models utilised by the heritage science community such as CIDOC CRM (ISO 21127:2006) and CRMsci.
- All data files stored in E-RIHS repositories should be in open, international., standardised file formats to ensure long-term interoperability in terms of usability, accessibility, and sustainability.

The Re-usability principle

- The research data in the field of heritage science must be prepared for future research and future processing.
- The output of RIHS researchers and laboratories must systematically be documented and the E-RIHS researchers and laboratories should maintain appropriate version control for research data.

- All the files, repositories, and resources should follow a precise and consistent naming convention.
- E-RIHS repositories should create guidelines recommending standardised, widely used file formats within the Heritage Science community.
- The information about sample provenance, laboratory names, methodology, and equipment must be included in the metadata.
- the (meta)data copyright and the licence applied should be clear to permit the widest reuse possible
- E-RIHS should adopt the Creative Commons licensing framework and align other frameworks used within E-RIHS with it.

Ontologies and Controlled Vocabularies for Quality Assessment

The adoption of ontologies and standardized vocabularies plays a crucial role in guaranteeing the quality of data and metadata within the DIGILAB ecosystem. Quality assessment is not limited to syntactic correctness; it also requires semantic consistency, interoperability, and compliance with community standards. Ontologies (for more details, about the DIGILAB semantic layer, see paragraph 4.3.2) and related extensions provide a formal conceptual framework that ensures data is represented in a structured, coherent, and machine-actionable manner. This approach eliminates ambiguity and supports advanced reasoning across heterogeneous datasets.

Similarly, the extensive use of controlled vocabularies ensures that descriptive terms are persistent, unambiguous, and interoperable. By enforcing the use of shared terminologies, DIGILAB guarantees that metadata is rich, consistent, and reusable across different research infrastructures and domains.

Integrating ontologies and vocabularies into the data lifecycle enables:

- Validation of semantic integrity during ingestion and transformation processes.
- Automated quality checks based on ontology-driven rules and constraints.
- Enhanced interoperability through mappings and semantic alignment.
- Improved reusability by providing clear, machine-readable relationships between entities.

This semantic approach strengthens the overall quality assurance framework, ensuring that data and metadata meet the highest standards of accuracy, completeness, and FAIR compliance, while supporting long-term sustainability and integration into federated environments

5.4 OPERAS: Quality Assessment

OPERAS focuses on providing and improving access rather than producing resources: pilot services/platform developed have an enabling function and are offered to the scientific community, rather than collecting resources produced by the OUs, although such resources are provided for testing and basic enrichment of the platforms.

Although the Italian node of OPERAS is in a starting phase, a data management plan with specific attention to the FAIR principles can be sketched, based on the expertise developed in OPERAS EU-projects like OPERAS-P and OPERAS-PLUS.

A. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

1. All digital objects in the OPERAS pilots are expected to receive persistent and unique identifiers as DOIs provided by CNR-ILIESI or other CNR-managed DOI series.
2. All contributors to the data published and managed within the pilots are expected to have ORCID-IDs or to be invited to create one.
3. Naming standards for files defined and followed.
4. The process on how to frame the resources published through the pilot services/platforms and consistently add metadata are expected to be defined in the design phase that has been foreseen as an essential component of the tenders.

B. Making data openly accessible

1. The principle “as open as possible, as closed as (strictly) necessary” is applied to all managed data.
2. The pilot services/platforms provide the tools to access the data.
3. All data and resources that can be exported from the pilot services/platforms are accessible using standard and open-source software. Documentation concerning software needed to access the data should not be required.
4. In principle, persons and entities accessing the data do not need to be identified. Harvesting of data in forms such as RDF Triples / DCAT-AP / OAI-PMH is provided.

C. Making data interoperable

1. Data and metadata structures comply with the H2IOSC project ontology that is defined in WP4. Reference is made as necessary to the Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies (SPAR).
2. The resources use, whenever appropriate, standard vocabularies and linked open data vocabularies, such as the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT), Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), and DDI-RDF Discovery Vocabulary (Disco).
3. A publicly perusable data summary is expected to be developed, kept, and updated.

D. Increasing data re-use (through open licences)

1. All resources produced, presented and managed through the OPERAS services/platforms use Creative Commons licences, including the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC-BY) and, for metadata, the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0).
2. Among the Creative Commons licences that allow for reuse and sharing, Open Culture licences are strongly encouraged, following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.
3. No embargoed data are published through the pilot services/platforms.

E. Other provisions

1. Specific adaptations of the management plan, e.g., for ethical aspects, are developed for single resources or sets of resources as needed, according to the governance model of the pilot services/platforms.
2. Data Security is ensured by the H2IOSC regulations for its data centres.

3. All information and processes needed to understand the applied principles of data collection, management, and publishing, are documented. All additional documentation produced by the OPERAS OUs in the H2IOSC project are managed according to the data management plan that is expected to be developed by H2IOSC and in compliance with that of the OPERAS.it JRU (the Italian OPERAS node).

The successful fairification of resources and FAIR publication is further ensured by quality policies and good management practices, in terms both of process and of results achieved, that are expected to be properly established and documented.

In order to efficiently validate national platforms, workflows, resources, data and metadata according to the FAIR principles, certification of procedures is expected to be designed in cooperation with OPERAS European certification tools and services.

5.4.1 Practical Cases

No practical case are presented at this stage.

6 GUIDELINES FOR COMMON POLICIES IMPLEMENTATION

The section is about open data and open access and relies on the policies about IPR and open data, and the frameworks enabling Open Access according to academic best practices and EU recommendations. It also reports on frameworks for Open Access and Open Data. It is conceived as a 'guide to good practice', and as such it includes examples, practical cases and answers to user questions.

6.1 CLARIN

Findable.

In respect of the FAIR principles, ILC4CLARIN assigns to each deposited resource a persistent identifier conforming to the (F1) principle in order to ensure that the resource is findable for every user into the repository. According to (F2) users are facilitated in describing items with a rich metadata schema conformed to the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative and Component MetaData Infrastructure standards. As stated in (F3), metadata are separated from data and accompany them during the storage into the repository. In the metadata file the PID of the resource is declared with the specific DC metadata element. To make data findable on the Internet (F4) ILC4CLARIN is listed in the Registry of Data Repositories re3Data.org under ID:r3d100012262 [14] the language archive, <http://www.language-archives.org/archive/dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it>, and it is indexed by SHARE and the Web of Science Data Citation Index.

Accessible.

The deposited items are immediately accessible via hyperlink through the protocol [http\(s\)](http(s)://) previous the user's authentication (A1.2). This process ensures the control of access on resources with privacy limitations. Resources are searchable via the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), a faceted browser developed within CLARIN with the aim to explore the deposited items in CLARIN. It provides an easy to use interface, allowing for a uniform search and discovery process for a large number of resources from a wide variety of domains and providers.

Interoperable.

To make resources much interoperable, users are recommended to use standard data formats during submission. Especially for language resources recommended formats, depositors are referred to <https://www.clarin.eu/sites/default/files/Standards%20for%20LRT-v6.pdf> from the FAQ page of ILC4CLARIN repository which provides the list of formats recommended by CLARIN (I1).

The repository uses ISO language codes in metadata and allows for a variety of data formats for the submitted digital objects, as described on the repository website (I2).

In the submission process, users are required to provide at least the main metadata for identifying the resource. Moreover, to enrich much more the Component MetaData Infrastructure provided by CLARIN to overcome the dispersion of information in different standards. The infrastructure is a framework to describe and reuse metadata blueprints shared with other users in the Component

Registry to promote reuse [CLARIN CD]. According to the specified resource type, the required metadata are different. (i.e. corpus, lexical/conceptual resource, tool, language description).

It is possible to disseminate the submission metadata in various formats (consulting list: <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/repository/oai/request?verb=ListMetadataFormats>) allowing to promote the submitted content in number of aggregators (and/or search engines).

Reusable.

Licensing status (R1.1) is specified by the submitter(s) to declare the use of the item(s) (dc.rights). For this option it is possible to choose between a wide range of licences. The full list is available at: <https://dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/page/licenses>.

CLARIN endorses the Data Citation Principles and thus ILC4CLARIN. Here the recommendations of RDA's Data Citation Work Group[DCWG] are implemented to help users to properly cite the items stored into the repository. In order to facilitate the support in citation, submitters are required to fill the proper elements and specify the whole ownerships and provenance history (R1.3).

The Dublin Core metadata standard (in its simple and qualified versions) is used for the description of resources. In particular the submission interface is based on this CMDI profile, a meta-model implemented with the aim of ensuring "semantic interoperability".

The repository has an advanced tool for browsing and searching items powered by Solr[Solr] based on full-text indexing of all text-based files in the repository as well as for faceted browsing of the repository metadata. The repository is regularly harvested by various institutions that reuse the metadata provided here: CLARIN ERIC, the reference RI, with the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) where language resources may be discovered using a faceted search engine. ILC4CLARIN is also registered to different archive initiatives, see OLAC[OLAC], Open Archives[Open Archives], DURASPACE[DURASPACE], ROAR[ROAR].

Each submission is given a PID that people are recommended to use for citation.

Open Access and Open Data.

To make data searchable and reusable, ILC4CLARIN distinguishes three levels of Licence agreements:

- 1) "Distribution Licence Agreement" [DLA]: where are described the rights and duties of the repository and the submitters affirm that they have the right to submit the data and give the repository centre the rights to distribute the data on their behalf. The repository requires submitters to electronically sign the right to archive the data and the agreement that the responsibility of the content lies with them. The author of the work will always remain the owner of the data. The repository stores a copy of the data which it must take good care of, according to the terms of the contract and the terms and conditions for use.
- 2) "Terms of Service of the ILC4CLARIN CLARIN-DSpace repository" [CLARIN ToS]: everyone who downloads data is bound by the licence assigned to the item: by using the search functions offered by the repository web interface and accessing or downloading the archived data the user agrees to the cited terms. Additionally, to download protected data, one has to be authenticated and needs to electronically sign a licence.

- 3) The repository licensing policy is based on the licence selected [CLARIN ToS] by the depositor when submitting his/her data. There are several available open licences a depositor can choose from directly in the interface within the submission workflow. There is also the possibility for users to contact the repository staff for setting-up custom further licences. The repository also enables the submitters to restrict access to their resources at various levels. This includes the possibility of assigning licences that must be electronically signed by authenticated users before they can get access to them. The ILC4CLARIN Centre at the Institute for Computational Linguistics specific terms of the licence. The repository keeps track of those signatures and because the authenticated users must be real people, this process is well defined. The repository also offers the option to put an embargo on submissions, which means that the submissions will be archived immediately after completion of the curation workflow, but they will become publicly available after a specific date.

6.1.1 Practical Case

Musisque Deoque (MQDQ) [MQDQ, 2005] (Figure 7) is a remarkable digital resource developed at the University of Venice, encompassing the entire corpus of Latin poets from its beginnings to the end of the VIIIth century. This comprehensive collection exemplifies the embodiment of the FAIR principles, ensuring that digital resources are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Firstly, its deposit in the CLARIN repository, specifically on the ILC4CLARIN repository, and its visibility through the Virtual Language Observatory of CLARIN ensures that it is easily Findable. The provided handle (<https://dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/handle/20.500.11752/OPEN-555>) serves as a persistent identifier, further enhancing its findability. In terms of Accessibility, the resource is available under the CC BY-SA 4.0 licence, promoting open access and sharing. The encoding in XML-TEI format ensures Interoperability, allowing the data to be seamlessly integrated and used in conjunction with other datasets and tools. Lastly, the comprehensive documentation, critical apparatuses, and the open licence ensure that MQDQ is Reusable, allowing researchers and educators to utilize the resource in various contexts while acknowledging its origins. Thus, MQDQ, with its roots at the University of Venice and its data housed in the ILC4CLARIN repository, stands as a paragon of the FAIR principles in the realm of digital resources.

Musisque Deoque (MQDQ)

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AA. VV., 2005, *Musisque Deoque (MQDQ)*, ILC-CNR for CLARIN-IT repository hosted at Institute for Computational Linguistics "A. Zampolli", National Research Council, in Pisa, <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11752/OPEN-555>.

Share:

Authors	AA. VV.
Project URL	http://www.mqdq.it
Demo URL	https://www.mqdq.it/public/ricerca/avanzata
Referenced by	https://jicl.org/content/2-allissues/13-Heft2-2011/17.pdf
Date issued	2005-01-01
Type	corpus, text
Size	2300000 tokens
Language(s)	AncientGreek (to 1453) , Latin
Description	Musisque Deoque, the whole corpus of the Latin poets, from the beginnings to the end of VIth century, was established at the end of 2005 with the main goal of creating a singular database of Latin poetry, supported by a critical and exegetical electronic apparatus. At present, main collections of classical texts have been transferred onto digital device while resources, mostly online, allow quicker lexical searches. In most cases, however, search engine inquirv only provides results of a kev inside a fix and 'authoritarian' text. The aim

Figure 4: Musisque Deoque metadata page in ILC4CLARIN repository

6.2 DARIAH

DARIAH, the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, recognizes the importance of data quality and legal compliance in managing digital assets. To ensure the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles are adhered to and promote open access and open data, DARIAH provides the following guidelines:

Data Quality

- Develop clear data management policies and procedures: Establish guidelines for data collection, curation, documentation, and preservation to ensure consistency and accuracy.
- Implement data validation and quality control processes: Use standardised metadata schemes, formats, and ontologies to enhance data quality and interoperability.
- Foster collaborative data curation: Encourage researchers and data providers to contribute to the improvement of data quality through active participation in data curation activities.

Legal Compliance

- Identify applicable laws and regulations: Understand the legal framework governing data collection, storage, and usage, including intellectual property rights, privacy, and data protection laws.
- Establish data governance frameworks: Create policies and procedures for data management that address legal requirements and ensure compliance with relevant regulations.

- Secure appropriate permissions and licences: Obtain necessary permissions from data providers and ensure compliance with licensing agreements to protect intellectual property rights and maintain legal compliance.
- Anonymize sensitive data: If dealing with user data, utilise anonymization techniques to protect individual privacy and comply with data protection regulations.

Open Access and Open Data

- Promote open access principles: Encourage researchers and data providers to make their data openly available to the research community, enabling broader access and reuse.
- Implement data sharing platforms: Establish repositories and platforms that adhere to open access and open data standards, facilitating the discovery and sharing of research data.
- Provide clear data licensing information: Encourage the use of open licences, such as Creative Commons, to specify the terms and conditions for data reuse and foster interoperability.

DARIAH emphasises the importance of continuous monitoring, evaluation, and improvement of data management practices to ensure ongoing data quality and legal compliance. By following these guidelines, researchers and institutions can contribute to the advancement of knowledge and facilitate collaboration in the arts and humanities research community.

6.3 E-RIHS

All the recommendations that the E-RIHS Infrastructure proposes to adopt to comply with the FAIR principles and the recommendations defined at national and European level for Open Access and Open Data were described in detail in the previous chapter. To understand the level of adherence of digital resources to the FAIR principles, surveys were conducted as part of WP2. The results of these activities form the foundation for the development phase of the E-RIHS DIGILAB platform. The E-RIHS community is engaged in many initiatives to translate the principles of Open science into concrete actions in order to increase the knowledge, conservation and enhancement of Cultural Heritage. Among the various initiatives aimed at responding to these challenges, we report two addressed in the last two years.

6.3.1 Practical case: the DataSpace-ISPC project

The design of the DIGILAB Data Infrastructure has been the subject of study by the DHILab group at ISPC in recent years, resulting in the configuration of a prototype that implements some of the main features that the DIGILAB Data Infrastructure should possess. The prototype, called ISPC Dataspace, has been developed based on the Arches platform [Arches] in version 6.2, with a specific focus on the modules implemented for Heritage Science: Arches for Science [Arches for Science]. It is freely accessible at the following address: <https://dataspace.ispc.cnr.it>

Figure 5: Homepage of DataSpace

DataSpace is a powerful data management platform for the sharing, accessing, and long-term data conservation produced by the Institute of Cultural Heritage Sciences. It allows access to innovative digital tools & services to increase knowledge and enhance the conservation of Cultural Heritage from an interdisciplinary perspective. DataSpace represents the first step towards the design of a shared and more general platform (DIGILAB) within the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS).

DataSpace provides access to research data, initially generated by HS researchers, curating it according to the FAIR data principles and enabling its interoperability to Virtual Research Environments, where they can access, visualise, interrogate, and manipulate such data, to create new Heritage-related knowledge.

Its architecture has been designed starting from results of European-related projects, i.e. E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS, and in dialogue with the E-RIHS- IP project (submitted at the call: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02-02). It will also be aligned with EU policies regarding data management (FAIR, Open Research Data) and the European Open Science Cloud strategy (EOSC).

DataSpace can also facilitate the exchange of data and their interoperability, promoting the development of open science in the heritage science field. It will offer virtual access to tools and data supporting multidisciplinary research (i.e. results of scientific measurement, environment for immersive and interactive visualisation of the dataset, historical documentation and literature sources, etc.). It guarantees data searchability with advanced tools based on metadata stored in federated repositories. It also grants accessibility of resources through mechanisms of federated identity, delegating access and delivery control to the nodes. Data interoperability is granted using appropriate and shared standards, while re-use is guaranteed by the possibility of data processing through specialised services (i.e. virtual access, scientific visualisation, and simulation for digital heritage, collaborative research in immersive and interactive environments accessible on-site or remotely, data georeferencing annotation, analysis, etc.) integrated into the E-RIHS ecosystem.

On DataSpace, users can input, store, and organise large amounts of data in a structured manner, ensuring data integrity and easy accessibility. With support for various data types, including geospatial data, DataSpace empowers users to handle and analyse related information effectively.

One of the key strengths of DataSpace lies in its data discovery capabilities. Users can easily search, filter, and retrieve specific data sets or subsets based on their desired criteria. This streamlined approach to data retrieval saves valuable time and allows users to focus on gaining insights from the data rather than struggling with manual searches.

DataSpace also offers powerful visualisation tools to enhance data exploration. The platform supports interactive maps, charts, and graphs, enabling users to gain insights from their data and effectively communicate their findings to others. DataSpace also has the capability to generate semantic data according to standards, which is significant because it enhances the possibility of creating data that can work well together and be maintained over time. Users can upload and utilise various ontologies, such as the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM). Once they create instances of objects, DataSpace generates a node map that illustrates the relationships between resources (see Figure 3).

Figure 6: Knowledge graph

About data models, ARCHES has a variety of features and capabilities for data management and allows for flexible customisation of the data model. To implement DataSpace, we used different modelling solutions, starting from heterogeneous digital resources managed in a completely different way. Currently, we evaluated the data of two projects, and we assumed them like case studies to compare the distinct solutions, their strengths and limits. The relationship between the abstraction level of data models and the need not to lose information about them is a crucial topic for reflection.

After engaging in discussions with researchers and various research groups within the Institute, we identified some projects and initiatives to prioritise in this initial phase of activities. In making our selection, we considered the Institute's diverse sectors, numerous themes, and various lines of

research, ensuring that the chosen projects originated from different disciplinary fields to address the needs and requirements of the relevant scientific communities. This approach allowed us to leverage diverse resources, encompassing disciplines such as archaeology, the history of illuminated manuscripts, architecture, and diagnostics for knowledge, conservation, and restoration of cultural heritage.

Simultaneously, the inclusion of projects from different disciplinary fields enabled us to understand specific researchers' needs, reconstruct workflows and operational processes followed by various stakeholders, and address specific conceptual models, as well as different types of data and resource management methods. Meeting these diverse requirements while designing the DataSpace and choosing appropriate technological solutions to harmonise the needs with the opportunities provided by Arches posed significant challenges throughout the project.

Within the DataSpace project, two case studies have been developed: the first dedicated to the Marmora Phrygiae research initiative (Figure 4) and the second to a corpus of illuminated manuscripts hosted in the Augusta Library in Perugia.

Figure 7: Screenshot DataSpace platform

6.3.2 Practical Case: 3D Roman Theatre in Catania, in SSHOC project.

Within the SSHOC project we developed a case study dedicated to the 3D reconstruction of the Roman Theater of Catania [Schmidle et al., 2022], addressing some crucial issues, regarding the quality of data and metadata, their long-term conservation, the definition of operative workflows and scientific transparency of research, the data reuse. To show how to ensure FAIR principles, through the combined use of the Extended Matrix methodology [Demetrescu, 2018] and EMviQ 4D inspection tool [Demetrescu et al., 2023].

Often in a virtual reconstruction process the efforts are mainly addressed to obtain an excellent and photorealistic outcome, not taking care of the risk of dramatically losing all the intermediate data processed and the knowledge of the process itself, which we want to make consistent with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) principles. Thus we need to consider and overcome some general issues inherent in the processes of virtual reconstruction of a cultural object.

For example, raw data collected during the survey campaign are often stored on various media without creating a proper data structure to preserve their logic and semantic meaning over time. Furthermore, the entire reasoning process is often described in a single scientific publication, which, although of value, describes the decisions taken in a narrative and non-specific way. Recently, these ambitious challenges have been addressed within the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project [SSHopencloud] as a dedicated case study of the Roman Catania theatre, for which we made a new virtual reconstruction. Part of the data collected to make it comes from earlier projects which provided a hypothetical reconstruction of the Roman theatre.

One of the main limitations to the shareability of the data and the scientific approach used to perform the first virtual reconstruction of the Roman Theatre of Catania is due to the massive use of commercial software solutions for data acquisition and processing. This resulted in the generation of a series of files in proprietary format that could only be opened and modified by having the corresponding licensed software.

In order to overcome this limitation and to make the dataset at the basis of the virtual reconstruction work open and interoperable, in accordance with FAIR principles, the first technical activity that was tackled was to export the 3D models from the proprietary Cinema4D format to the open Blender format.

Figure 8: Export from C4D to Blender in OBJ format

To make the data accessible and integrated between them, the metaphor of the knowledge graph was used and in particular the formalism in which it is possible to connect the data to their three-dimensional representations.

Another key aspect for dissemination was the development of an online tool capable of reading the EM database in open format and making it searchable and viewable within a browser. This tool, named EMviq was developed within the framework ATON.

The work of data interchange is made possible if the service platforms are able to talk to each other in an effective way. For this reason, particular effort has been made in the design and execution of tools for data exchange between ATON 3 and Matrix and iDAI collaborative tools.

In order to make the EM knowledge graph approach compatible with the other databases present in the iDAI tools, a first mapping of EM with CIDOC CRM has been developed. This is the culmination of an effort that lasted several months in collaboration with colleagues at the Polytechnic of Turin.

Figure 9: Three different extraction steps from an Extended Matrix

6.4 OPERAS

According to the OPERAS vision and policy, the large-scale adoption of Diamond OA model is consistent with academic best practices and EU recommendations, allowing for high quality scientific content to be made available freely and immediately. The adoption of best practices in academic publishing contribute to expand and to facilitate the transition to Diamond OA publication of journals and monographs in the SSH research field at national and European level. Currently the aim is to trace the standards at platform and inter-platform level and identify key areas for their implementation (WP2).

6.4.1 Practical Case

The above mentioned policies are expected to be applied to all the databases and resources made available in the platform. The same policies determine the output of the Digital Scholarship editions workflows (wherever possible), and of the grey literature assessment and DOA publishing platform, developed in WP7.T11.

The OPERAS OUs collaborate with the Italian national node and the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA European projects in supporting and strengthening institutional capacity building for OA publishing, contributing to the H2IOSC commitment to raise scholarly publishing standards.

Moreover, the involvement of the research community in the co-design of the prototypes during the pilot services/platforms development eventually provide a proper case study for the implementation of common Open Science policies and Diamond OA practices in the H/CH ecosystem.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The Deliverable 3.1 is a product of the combined efforts of the different partners that worked together in WP3. It marks a key achievement in the H2IOSC project, laying the groundwork for the harmonization of data management policies, quality assurance frameworks, and interoperability strategies across multiple research infrastructures in the humanities and cultural heritage domain.

Through an analysis of existing practices and the identification of critical gaps, this deliverable provides a set of guidelines addressing all phases of the data lifecycle, ranging from production and curation to long-term preservation and publication, while ensuring full compliance with FAIR principles, Open Access, and Open Data recommendations.

The activities carried out enabled the consolidation of methodological approaches and the definition of common standards. These efforts foster semantic interoperability and facilitate the integration of heterogeneous resources into a unified, federated ecosystem. Practical case studies included in the deliverable illustrate the applicability of these guidelines and demonstrate tangible progress in implementing best practices within the participating infrastructures.

Looking forward, these guidelines will serve as a strategic foundation for the next phase of the H2IOSC cluster, which has to focus on:

- Operationalizing shared policies across all infrastructures to ensure consistency and scalability.
- Enhancing FAIRification processes to improve data discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.
- Strengthening quality assessment mechanisms for repositories, data, and metadata, aligning with international certification standards.
- Ensuring sustainability and scalability of the proposed solutions to support long-term adoption and integration into other frameworks.

By implementing these recommendations, the RIs Cluster established under the H2IOSC project successfully contributed to the creation of a robust, collaborative environment supported by effective tools and platforms for the humanities and cultural heritage research domain. This integrated ecosystem now enables seamless data sharing, promotes data reuse, and fosters innovation across disciplines. These achievements advance the principles of Open Science and reinforce the strategic role of cultural heritage in the digital research landscape.

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